

Thermodynamics of oxidation and nitridation reactions of boron carbide

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Boron carbide, an extremely hard material that is used in lightweight body armour and nuclear reactors, requires to be sintered at high temperature to form appropriate shapes. The quality and hardness of the product is affected by oxidative processes and reaction with traces of nitrogen in air. Information on the thermodynamics of such processes is quite limited. In this work, computational study of the thermodynamics of reactions of B_4C with oxygen and nitrogen has been undertaken. This includes derivation of equilibrium constant ($\log k$)-temperature relations and equilibrium O_2/N_2 activities-temperature relations in the region 273–2300 K, for all possible reactions with O_2 and N_2 . Reaction phase diagrams were then derived to depict the reaction that is thermodynamically most favourable under the T-P- O_2/N_2 conditions. All computations were done with a program in *Mathematica*, developed for this purpose. Results reveal that $\log k$ values for all oxidative reactions are positive and those producing the trioxide (B_2O_3) are energetically most favoured. Reaction phase diagrams show that B_4C is stable only at extremely low O_2 pressures and under high concentrations of gaseous components; the B moiety is more susceptible to oxidation compared to C moiety. When heated, initially B_2O_3 is formed regardless of concentration of gases. Similar behaviour is observed in N_2 , where BN is produced at the lowest temperatures but is stable at higher temperatures. It is concluded that a surface layer of B_2O_3 produced initially serves as a protective shield against catastrophic oxidation of B_4C .

Keywords: B_4C , oxidation, nitridation, reaction, phase diagram, boron oxides, nitride, equilibrium constant, program.

Introduction

Boron carbide is an extremely hard ceramic material used in ballistic armour, where the combination of high hardness, high elastic modulus, and low density gives the material an exceptionally high specific stopping power to defeat high velocity projectiles. It is also used in the nuclear industry as components of shields and control rods because of its high neutron absorption capacity. Boron carbide is the third hardest material known, after diamond and boron nitride.

Application of boron carbide to form articles of desired shapes require sintering; sintering of boron carbide is a difficult operation due to its high melting point of 2763°C combined with low oxidation resistance beyond 1000°C. One of the reasons for the problems in sintering B_4C , is the presence of oxide coatings on the surfaces of the grains. Such coatings of B_2O_3 could form during the production of B_4C or even later during the sintering process itself in the presence of minute traces of oxygen. In thermodynamic studies of oxidation of SiC¹, we observed that reactions of the type $SiC + 2O_2 \rightarrow SiO_2 + CO_2$ and $SiC + 1.5O_2 \rightarrow SiO_2 + CO$ are ther-

modynamically very favourable at 1600°C even at partial pressures of oxygen as low as 10^{-16} . Similar reactions could occur in B_4C as: $B_4C + 4O_2 = 2B_2O_3 + CO_2$. Consequently, liquid B_2O_3 would cover the surface of B_4C particles as a thin film. This would prevent interparticle bonding and retard densification. Above 1840°C, B_2O_3 would evaporate with the formation of pores². In order to reduce problems in densification caused by oxidation coatings, sintering is usually done under high vacuum or in an inert gas atmosphere or by using additives like C, TiC, SiC, etc.³⁻⁵.

Experimental studies on the oxidation of boron carbide are not extensive. It was reported⁶ that oxidation of B_4C starts at around 600°C and increases rapidly at 1200°C; above 1200°C, B_2O_3 forms a volatile glass which not only vaporises but also transports oxygen rapidly. Water vapour enhances oxidation, reduces temperature of B_2O_3 volatilisation and consequently above 900°C, the oxide film is no longer protective⁷. It was observed that oxidation of B_4C was para linear and results in depletion of C from the surface⁸. Particle size strongly influences oxidation rates with smaller particles

being more rapidly oxidised⁹. According to them, the rate limiting step is the diffusion of oxygen through the oxide layer and is also influenced by the volatilisation rates of B₂O₃.

Thermodynamic studies on reactions of boron carbides with oxygen appears to be limited. Earlier the present authors undertook theoretical studies on the thermodynamics of oxidation of cubic SiC¹. Oxidation by atomic oxygen (O) and ozone (O₃) was derived to understand the thermodynamic stability of SiC in the upper atmosphere. Temperature relationship of equilibrium constant (*k*) was derived. The *k* values for all reactions were highly positive and the reaction forming SiO₂ + CO₂ was thermodynamically the most favourable¹. With increasing levels of O or O₃, the first products were SiO₂ + C, followed by SiO₂ + CO or SiO + CO₂. The Si atom in the SiC crystal was more susceptible, being oxidised first to SiO₂¹.

In this work, we undertook theoretical studies of the thermodynamics of reactions of B₄C with O₂ and N₂. Equilibrium constant (*k*)-temperature (T) relationships and oxygen partial pressure (P)-temperature (T) relationships were derived for all possible reactions with O₂ and N₂. Finally, reaction phase diagrams for oxidation and nitridation of B₄C were derived using a computer program developed here. These phase diagrams depict the reaction that is thermodynamically most favourable under the T-P conditions. It is expected that these thermodynamic studies of the oxidation of B₄C as a function of oxygen partial pressure and temperature would provide a much needed understanding of the theoretical basis of the reactions and function as an important aid in improving sintering conditions. It could also help to find suitable partial pressure and temperature windows to avoid oxidation. Moreover, this will provide an understanding of how oxygen interferes with the sintering kinetics at different oxygen partial pressures.

Theory and methods:

In the first step, balanced equations for all possible reactions of B₄C with O₂ and N₂ were constructed. Standard free energy change of the reactions ($\Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ}$) were calculated from the relation

$$\Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{f,T}^{\circ}(\text{products}) - \Delta G_{f,T}^{\circ}(\text{reactants}) \quad (1)$$

Equilibrium constant (*k*) is obtained from the relation

$$\Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ} = -RT \ln k \quad (2)$$

which can also be expressed in terms of the activities of the products and reactants as

$$\Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ} = -RT \ln \Pi a_p^{\nu} / \Pi a_r^k \quad (3)$$

where *a_p* and *a_r* are the activities of product and reactant respectively and the power terms are the stoichiometric amounts in the reaction. Total free energy change under any given condition ($\Delta G_{r,T}$) is then obtained from the standard free energy change as:

$$\Delta G_{r,T} = \Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ} + RT \ln \Pi a_p^{\nu} / \Pi a_r^k \quad (4)$$

Derivation of reaction phase diagrams broadly follows the methodology developed earlier^{1,10,11} that involves the following steps: (i) computation of free energy change of reaction ($\Delta G_{r,T}$) for all possible reactions in a system, (ii) comparison of $\Delta G_{r,T}$ of all reactions to obtain the reaction showing greatest reduction in free energy and (iii) derivation of the limiting conditions for the reaction to have largest free energy reduction compared to all other reactions (boundary conditions). In order to obtain the boundary conditions, eq. (4) is derived for small intervals of the variables, *a_r*¹ (here P_{O₂}) and T. The derived values are compared for each defined value of the variables and thereby transition boundaries are obtained¹². The following components contribute to the equilibrium: B₄C, B, C, B₂O₃, B₂O, BO, B₂O₂, BO₂, CO, CO₂ and O₂. There are 5 phases, viz. B₄C, B, C, B₂O₃ and the gases. Therefore, the degrees of freedom (F) are 8, and to comply with phase rule, 6 F need to be defined (fixed constant values) for a 2D diagram with 2 variables. These include, B₂O, BO, B₂O₂, BO₂, CO and CO₂. The variables in the oxidation reaction are temperature (T) and partial pressure of O₂(P_{O₂}). All these factors greatly increase the complexity of the reaction phase diagrams. For nitridation reactions, conforming to phase rule requires one component to be defined, viz. C₂N₂, with the reaction variables being temperature and partial pressure of N₂(P_{N₂}).

Thermodynamic data for all calculations were obtained from the NIST-JANAF tables¹³. Calculations were performed using programs developed in *Mathematica*. The first level program (EQBO, Supplementary 1) calculates equilibrium constant-temperature and partial pressure-temperature relations (Fig. 1). Using values of standard free energy of formation at various temperatures ($\Delta G_{f,T}^{\circ}$), the standard free energy change of reaction ($\Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ}$) for all reactions, 1-17 (Table 1), are derived. Then equilibrium constants (log *k*) values are derived followed by equilibrium O₂ partial pressures (P_{O₂}). The list of $\Delta G_{r,T}^{\circ}$ -T is exported for use by the second program. The second level program (PDBO, Supplementary 2) derives reaction phase diagrams in a 2D axis (T-

Fig. 1. Flowchart for the programs EQBO and PDBO to derive equilibrium oxygen activities and oxidation phase diagrams.

log P_{O_2}). Both programs are available in executable form (.nb files) as well as pdf files.

Flow chart for the main program (PDBO) is shown in Fig. 1. The various steps include: (i) importing the list of T-, $\Delta G_{r,T}^0$ data, (ii) deriving linear regression equations for the same, (iii) computing $\Delta G_{r,T}^0$ for small increments of T (every 10 K)

and log P_{O_2} (every 10^{-1} atm), (iv) computing total free energy change of reaction, $\Delta G_{r,T}$, for all reactions at all values of T and P_{O_2} , (v) discarding reactions with positive values of $\Delta G_{r,T}$ after assigning a string value to them, (vi) finding minimum values of $\Delta G_{r,T}$ at every point on the P-T space, (vii) identifying reactions producing those minimum $\Delta G_{r,T}$ values

Table 1. Oxidation reactions of B₄C

Reaction number	Reaction stoichiometry
1	B ₄ C + 7/2O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O ₃ + CO
2	B ₄ C + 4O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O ₃ + CO ₂
3	B ₄ C + 3O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O ₃ + C
4	B ₄ C + 3/2O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O + CO
5	B ₄ C + 2O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O + CO ₂
6	B ₄ C + O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O + C
7	B ₄ C + 5/2O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O ₂ + CO
8	B ₄ C + 3O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O ₂ + CO ₂
9	B ₄ C + 2O ₂ ↔ 2B ₂ O ₂ + C
10	B ₄ C + 1/2O ₂ ↔ 4B + CO
11	B ₄ C + O ₂ ↔ 4B + CO ₂
12	B ₄ C + 5/2O ₂ ↔ 4BO + CO
13	B ₄ C + 3O ₂ ↔ 4BO + CO ₂
14	B ₄ C + 2O ₂ ↔ 4BO + C
15	B ₄ C + 9/2O ₂ ↔ 4BO ₂ + CO
16	B ₄ C + 5O ₂ ↔ 4BO ₂ + CO ₂
17	B ₄ C + 4O ₂ ↔ 4BO ₂ + C

at every point on the P-T space and (viii) plotting the reaction with the minimum $\Delta G_{r,T}$ value as a coloured box into the P-T space. Computations were done in the temperature range 500 K to 2300 K at intervals of 10 K; partial pressures of B₂O, BO, B₂O₂, BO₂, CO and CO₂ needed for eq. (4), were assigned values 10⁰, 10⁻⁵ or 10⁻¹⁵ to represent a range of conditions.

Results

Equilibrium constants and equilibrium gas pressure:

There are 17 possible reactions of B₄C with O₂ (Table 1) and 3 ways in which B₄C can react with N₂ (Table 2). Table 3 shows equilibrium constants (log *k*) at various temperatures (T) for all reactions with O₂. Oxidation can result in any of the five oxides of boron of which only B₂O₃ is not a gas. Reaction 2 producing B₂O₃ + CO₂ is most favoured with the highest values of log *k*, followed by reaction 1 producing B₂O₃ + CO and then by reaction 3 forming B₂O₃ + C. All reactions except 6, are thermodynamically favoured having positive values of log *k*. Reaction 6 producing B₂O + C, has negative values of log *k* up to 1000 K. Comparison of log *k* for reactions producing B₂O₃ with different oxidation states of carbon (reactions 1, 2, 3, Table 3a), shows that the reaction producing CO₂ (reaction 2) is thermodynamically most favorable followed by reactions yielding CO (reaction 1) and C (reaction 3) in that order. A similar trend is observed in reactions producing B₂O (reactions 4–6, Table 3a) where reaction 5 producing CO₂ has the highest value of log *k*, followed

Table 2. Nitridation reactions of B₄C

Reaction number	Reaction stoichiometry
1	B ₄ C + 2N ₂ ↔ 4BN + C
2	2B ₄ C + 5N ₂ ↔ 8BN + C ₂ N ₂
3	2B ₄ C + N ₂ ↔ 8B + C ₂ N ₂

Table 3a. Equilibrium constants (log *k*) for oxidation reactions 1–9

Temperature (K)	Reaction number								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
298.15	434.7	479.7	410.6	-4.6	40.5	-28.6	179.8	224.8	155.8
500	249.9	274.9	233.7	4.0	29.0	-12.3	110.3	135.3	94.0
1000	114.7	124.9	104.2	10.0	20.2	-0.5	58.9	69.1	48.4
1500	70.6	75.9	62.1	11.7	17.0	3.2	41.6	47.0	33.1
2000	48.7	51.5	41.2	12.4	15.3	5.0	32.9	35.8	25.4
2300	40.1	42.1	33.1	12.6	14.6	5.6	29.4	31.4	22.4

Table 3b. Equilibrium constants (log *k*) for oxidation reactions 10–17

Temperature (K)	Reaction number								
	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
298.15	17.3	62.4	37.2	82.2	13.1	220.6	265.7	196.6	
500	12.3	37.3	32.1	57.1	15.9	135.1	160.1	118.9	
1000	8.5	18.8	28.1	38.3	17.7	72.0	82.3	61.6	
1500	7.3	12.6	26.5	31.8	18.0	51.0	56.3	42.5	
2000	6.7	9.6	25.5	28.4	18.0	40.4	43.3	32.9	
2300	6.4	8.4	25.0	27.0	18.0	36.2	38.1	29.1	

by reaction 4 with CO and reaction 6 producing C. Reactions producing BO and BO₂ also have similar trends of decreasing log *k*, viz. BO + CO₂ > BO + CO > BO + C and BO₂ + CO₂ > BO₂ + CO > BO₂ + C. It may be inferred that CO₂ formation is most favoured rather than CO or C (graphite).

Similarly, when comparing the oxidation of the B moiety with the C moiety (reactions 3 and 11), log *k* values show that oxidation yielding the products B₂O₃ + C has about 5 times higher values than oxidation to the products B + CO₂ (Table 3). Therefore, from a thermodynamic standpoint, the oxidation of B in the crystal is favoured over oxidation of C.

Equilibrium O₂ activities (Fig. 2) reveal that at 1500 K, reactions forming B₂O₃ occur at very low oxygen pressures (legends 1, 2 and 3 in Fig. 2a and c) which is in the region of 10⁻⁴⁰ atm. Under standard activities of the gases (CO₂, BO, etc.) and 1500 K, oxidation does not occur with log O₂ < -20 (Fig. 2a and b); however, when activities of the gaseous products are very low, oxidation is favoured at log O₂ < 10⁻³⁰ (Fig. 2c and d). At lower temperatures, oxygen pressures have greater influence than at higher temperatures. The reactions are dependent on the levels of the gaseous products (CO₂, CO, B₂O, BO, BO₂ and B₂O₂). Accumulation (increase in pressure) of any of these gases raises the tolerance to oxidation and oxidation occurs at higher P_{O₂} pressures.

Log *k*-T relations for the nitridation reactions of B₄C are shown in Table 4. Reaction 2 producing BN + C₂N₂ has the highest value of log *k*, followed by reaction 1 producing BN + C. Reaction 3 (Table 4), in which B + C₂N₂ is obtained, has high negative values of log *k*. It appears that thermodynamically, the nitridation of B and C is favoured while selective nitridation of the C leaving a B residue is not favoured. For all reactions, equilibrium constants reduce sharply with temperature.

Equilibrium N₂ activities for the reactions (Fig. 3a) shows that under standard conditions, B₄C can be stable in presence of N₂ where log P_{N₂} = -10 at 1500 K. With very low partial pressures of the gaseous product, C₂N₂, tolerance to nitridation is reduced (Fig. 4b). The formation of boron nitride is thermodynamically favoured at low N₂ partial pressures; cyanogen gas may be evolved or graphitic C may form.

Reaction phase diagrams – Oxidation and nitridation:

The thermodynamically most stable reaction phases formed on oxidation of B₄C when exposed to varying partial pressures of O₂ and at varying levels of the gases CO₂, CO,

Table 4. Equilibrium constants (log *k*) for nitridation reactions 1–3

Temperature (K)	Reaction number		
	1	2	3
298.15	151.0	249.8	-65.5
500	82.6	135.0	-38.1
1000	32.1	50.2	-17.8
1500	15.4	22.2	-10.9
2000	7.1	8.4	-7.4
2300	3.9	3.1	-5.9

B₂O, BO, BO₂ and B₂O₂, are presented in Figs. 4a-c. Fig. 4a is the reaction equilibrium diagram when the gases CO₂, CO, B₂O, BO, BO₂ and B₂O₂ are at standard pressure (1 atm). At standard activities of the gaseous products, B₄C is stable up to log P_{O₂} of -20 at around 1500 K (Fig. 4a). At temperatures between 1750–2300 K, as P_{O₂} increases, B₂O and CO are first formed. On increasing P_{O₂}, oxidation to B₂O₃ and CO occurs. With further increase in P_{O₂}, both boron and carbon are completely oxidised to B₂O₃ and CO₂ (Fig. 4a). At lower temperatures (below ~1400 K), oxidation proceeds through the formation of B₂O₃ and C (as graphite) and subsequently to B₂O₃ and CO or B₂O₃ and CO₂. It is evident from the diagrams that the B atom is oxidised first regardless of oxygen partial pressures.

When partial pressures of the gaseous reaction products are lowered to 10⁻⁵ (Fig. 4b), the stability region of B₄C reduces considerably; it is only stable at log P_{O₂} < -32 atm. Oxidation routes are similar to those observed at standard conditions (Fig. 4a). At temperatures > 1750 K, oxidation proceeds as B₂O + CO, BO + CO, BO₂ + CO and BO₂ + CO₂, in that order with increasing oxygen pressures (Fig. 4b). Oxidation under very low levels of the gaseous products such as in evacuated systems proceeds differently. B₄C is no longer thermodynamically stable (Fig. 4c) under the conditions studied. At log P_{O₂} < -20, the suboxide B₂O and CO are the favoured products. Further increase in oxygen results in BO₂ and CO, followed by BO₂ and CO₂. B₂O₃ is formed only at lower temperatures (<1000 K). If B₄C at 1500 K is exposed to increasing levels of O₂, oxidation starts with B₂O + CO, then proceeds to BO + CO, subsequently to BO₂ + CO and finally to BO₂ + CO₂ at the highest oxygen levels.

It is noteworthy that if B₄C is slowly heated from room temperature, initially B₂O₃ is formed regardless of concentrations of gases. Since B₂O₃ is solid, it will form a protective layer on the surface. B₂O₃ melts at 723 K and boils at 2130

Fig. 2. Equilibrium O_2 activities for oxidation reactions of B_4C , (a) and (b) at $\log [CO_2] = 0$, $\log [CO] = 0$, $\log [BO] = 0$, $\log [B_2O] = 0$, $\log [BO_2] = 0$, $\log [B_2O_2] = 0$ and (c) and (d) at $\log [CO_2] = -15$, $\log [CO] = -15$, $\log [BO] = -15$, $\log [B_2O] = -15$, $\log [BO_2] = -15$, $\log [B_2O_2] = -15$. Numerals 1–17 indicate the reactions as shown in Table 1.

K; therefore, the protective action would continue up to 2100 K. In the range of 723–2130 K, there could be increased diffusion of O_2 through the liquid layer of B_2O_3 . Thermodynamic derivations suggest that the thermal stability of B_4C can be attributed to the formation of a non-gaseous oxide coating which functions as a protective layer.

Reaction phase diagram for nitridation of B_4C (Fig. 5a) reveals that in the presence of N_2 gas and under standard activity of C_2N_2 , B_4C is stable at high temperatures and reaction occurs only on increasing N_2 pressures. On increasing temperatures and N_2 pressures, nitride is formed together with C or C_2N_2 , depending on partial pressure of N_2 . Higher

Fig. 3. Equilibrium N_2 activities for oxidation reactions of B_4C , at (a) $\log [C_2N_2] = 0$ and (b) at $\log [C_2N_2] = -15$. Numerals 1–3 indicate the reactions as shown in Table 2.

N_2 activity favours formation of BN and C_2N_2 . A small region of graphitic formation together with BN is also observed (Fig. 5a and b). Fig. 5b shows a region in the temperature and pressure range of 1800–2500 K and 10^{-10} – 10^{-5} atm respectively where B and C_2N_2 will be produced. At P_{N_2} below $\sim 10^{-5}$, boron nitride will not form and B_4C will remain stable at 1750 K. This may provide a suitable atmosphere for sinter-

Fig. 4. Oxidation phase diagrams for B_4C at (a) $\log [CO_2], \log [CO], \log [BO], \log [B_2O], \log [BO_2], \log [B_2O_2] = 0$; (b) $\log [CO_2], \log [CO], \log [BO], \log [B_2O], \log [BO_2], \log [B_2O_2] = -5$ and (c) $\log [CO_2], \log [CO], \log [BO], \log [B_2O], \log [BO_2], \log [B_2O_2] = -15$. Numerals 1–17 indicate the reactions as shown in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Nitridation phase diagrams for B_4C at (a) $\log [C_2N_2] = 0$ and (b) at $\log [C_2N_2] = -15$. Numerals 1–3 indicate the reactions as shown in Table 2.

ing since initial flushing with nitrogen gas would scrub O_2 from the system.

Conclusions

Thermodynamic derivations show that oxidation reactions of B_4C have high equilibrium constants and can occur even with traces of oxygen. There are 17 ways in which B_4C can react with O_2 and 3 ways in which it can react with N_2 and almost all of these reactions are thermodynamically highly favourable. Oxidation phase diagrams show that different oxides of boron may form depending on pressures of gaseous components and temperature. The B atom is oxidised before oxidation of C. At lower temperatures, B_2O_3 is formed;

higher temperatures favour formation of B_2O , BO and BO_2 in that order with increasing O_2 partial pressures. However, highly favourable oxidation thermodynamics does not imply that boron carbide would necessarily undergo complete oxidation under any of these conditions. A surface layer of B_2O_3 is formed in the early stages of heating. This would greatly reduce diffusion of O_2 to the interior of the crystal and thus prevent further oxidation. The accumulation of CO_2 due to oxidation of C in B_4C would also reduce the oxygen pressures required to further oxidise B_4C . Derivations suggest that it would be difficult to completely retard surface oxidation because the partial pressures of oxygen have to be at levels that are difficult to obtain by vacuum. On the contrary, B_4C is quite stable in the presence of N_2 gas at high temperatures. Thus, an alternative is to scrub the system with nitrogen gas (or inert gas) or with an oxygen consuming material like carbon monoxide. These may be effective provided other reactions do not occur to change the chemical nature of the system.

Supplementary material

Programs used in these derivations are available online in executable forms and pdf versions at <https://1drv.ms/f/s!AqjYfZ29bJoNiAuW4Qm9UIHVSAJg>.

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